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**China and the Arctic—
Science, Security, and Governance**

POLICY BRIEF

Summary

The Arctic region has over the past decade emerged as an increasingly important dimension of China's international affairs. This is an outcome of two trends in world politics. On the one hand, the warming of the Arctic region creates the perception that the region is opening and with it the possibility of exploiting its natural resources and shorter shipping lanes. On the other, the international system has witnessed the Rise of China — the massive accumulation of wealth of the People's Republic of China (PRC). The Chinese Communist Party (CCP), which governs the PRC, has used this wealth to expand its power and influence beyond its immediate neighbourhood — including in the Arctic.

This policy brief introduces the PRC's Arctic scientific activities and capabilities, including its research infrastructure, long-term goals, and the significance of China's understanding of the region. By examining the region from a Chinese security perspective, the policy brief will show how Arctic engagement can boost aspects of the PRC's ecological, military, economic, technological, and political security. Finally, the policy brief discusses the PRC's official and academic positions regarding Arctic governance and the views of the region within bilateral relations with Arctic states, outlining the science-security-governance nexus in China's Arctic engagement.

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Key Messages

- ⇒ The PRC is pursuing a national strategy of the Great Rejuvenation of the Chinese Nation with China as a global leader in composite national strength and international influence. The CCP is restructuring the Chinese economy through innovation-led growth, a massive military modernization program and adopting security and development-oriented initiatives.
- ⇒ The PRC attaches significant political, economic, and military importance to the strategic new frontiers – cyberspace, the polar regions, the deep sea, and outer space. In all of these domains, the PRC has the ambition to establish itself as a great power that can shape its governance structures.
- ⇒ In 2018, the PRC government published China's official Arctic White Paper which identifies China as a near-Arctic state and an important Arctic stakeholder with policy priorities: understanding the Arctic, protecting the Arctic, developing the Arctic, and participating in regional governance.
- ⇒ China aims for a multidimensional Arctic research and monitoring system that includes research stations, icebreakers, meteorological platforms, buoys, unmanned systems, and polar-orbiting satellites.
- ⇒ The PRC supports the Arctic Council (AC) as the most important regional forum. At the same time, the PRC sees room for improvements in regional governance, particularly when it comes to the roles of AC observers.
- ⇒ In the last decade, the Arctic has emerged as an area of pragmatic cooperation (economic as well as scientific) between the PRC and Russia. China has invested in Russian Arctic LNG projects while Russia is now more open to Chinese involvement in the development of the Northern Sea Route.
- ⇒ Sino-American Arctic relations have deteriorated, reflecting the impacts of the unfolding great power competition between Beijing and Washington. The Chinese perceive the American return to the Arctic as a reflection of Washington's Cold War mentality to suppress China.

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Background

Since becoming the leader of the People's Republic of China (PRC) in 2012, the General Secretary of the Chinese Communist Party (CCP), Xi Jinping, has been pursuing a national strategy of the Great Rejuvenation of the Chinese Nation. Domestically, this transforms the PRC into a prosperous nation where citizen living standards are continuously improving and poverty is eradicated. Internationally, the goal is to restore China's dominance, centrality and prestige in Asia (and beyond) --to reshape the international order, reform global governance and become a global leader with both national strength and international influence (Xi 2017).

To achieve national rejuvenation, the CCP is actively restructuring the Chinese economy to an innovation-driven model, based on advanced manufacturing, self-reliance and a focus on the technologies of the so-called 'Fourth Industrial Revolution' (semiconductors, Artificial Intelligence, biotechnology etc.) (Doshi 2021). There is a critical role for science and technology in this restructuring as the PRC recognises that industrial revolutions shape global power distributions. This results in the CCP, which views science as a tool to advance its security and economic needs, to continuously increase China's R&D funding and eclipsing competitors such as Japan and the EU.

In the security domain, Xi is focusing on the modernisation of the Chinese armed forces to attain the status of a world-class military by 2049. This includes continuous budget increases, investments in power projection capabilities (such as aircraft carriers) and the enlargement of China's nuclear arsenal. To advance this goal, Xi is pursuing a 'Military-Civil Fusion Strategy' which is a two-way exchange of knowledge, information and practices between the military and civilian sectors in the PRC (Fritz 2021). At the same time, Xi has also expanded the notion of security in China. The Comprehensive National Security Outlook, introduced in 2014, now lists 16 types of security (political, ecological, technological, military, cultural etc.). This effectively intertwines security and development to hedge against domestic and international risks.

In foreign affairs, the PRC is much more proactive and forceful in safeguarding its core interests (i.e. such as the Taiwan issue). The CCP maintains that the world is undergoing changes unseen in a century, driven by emerging economies such as the PRC and that global governance is in dire need of reform. The PRC sees itself as providing solutions to the problems of global governance in the form of various Chinese initiatives such as the Global Security Initiative. The ultimate goal is to establish a Community of Shared Future for Mankind which will be based on win-win cooperation, dialogues, inclusive economic globalisation and opposition to power politics (SCIO 2023).

Under Xi, the PRC government attaches significant political, economic and military importance to the so-called strategic new frontiers – cyberspace, the polar regions, the deep seas and outer space. The PRC wants to establish itself as a great power in all of these domains, linking them to its Belt and Road Initiative while maintaining the need to participate in the formulation of the rules governing these frontiers. When it comes to the Arctic, the PRC is constructing a Polar Silk Road and aims to transform itself into a Polar Great Power (Brady 2017).

The PRC and Arctic Science

The PRC began its substantive engagement in Arctic scientific research in the mid-1990s by joining the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) and launching its first official Arctic scientific expedition in 1999. Today, China operates two Arctic research stations—one on Svalbard, Norway, and another in Iceland. It utilizes advanced research icebreakers, including the Xuelong and Xuelong 2, to support its activities. These icebreakers serve as mobile laboratories conducting research across the Arctic Ocean and adjacent seas.

By the end of 2025, China plans to operate five such vessels, reflecting its commitment to Arctic exploration. As of December 2024, Chinese scientists have completed 14 Arctic expeditions, typically conducted during summer months and lasting 70 to 90 days. These missions focus on disciplines such as climate studies, oceanography, marine biology, and sea ice formation. Recently, China has enhanced its capabilities with technologies like domestically constructed autonomous underwater vehicles, low-orbit satellites, buoys and meteorological stations enabling more precise environmental data collection. The goal is to build an integrated space, atmosphere, land, ice and underwater multi-dimensional scientific observation and monitoring network (Kossa 2024).

The Polar Research Institute of China (PRIC), based in Shanghai, coordinates China's polar research efforts. In addition to natural sciences, PRIC hosts a Division of Polar Strategic Studies, which examines Arctic politics, economics, and security. The PRC is expected to further deepen its Arctic scientific engagement as polar research is one of the priorities of China's 14th five-year development plan. Arctic scientific engagement is seen as a vehicle for international Arctic research cooperation that supports exchanges between China and Arctic states, and which also manages (to a certain point) to alleviate suspicions of China's Arctic presence.

The Arctic and China's Security

The PRC's engagement with the Arctic can also enhance numerous aspects of China's security. As a country that is increasingly susceptible to the effects of global climate change, understanding the changes that are taking place in the Arctic and their effects on the Chinese mainland have important implications for China's ecological security – the ability to address major internal and external ecological challenges – as there seem to be connections between variations in the Arctic environment and weather anomalies in East Asia.

In terms of military security, the Chinese armed forces have not yet ventured into the Arctic, but they are increasingly active in sub-Arctic waters, particularly in the Bering Sea. In 2024, the Chinese Coast Guard conducted joint patrols with the Russian Coast Guard in waters above the Arctic Circle in the Far East (Edvardsen and Martinussen 2024). Chinese military analysts value the Arctic for its geostrategic location as strategic commanding heights that connect and overlook three important political and economic areas – North America, Europe and Asia.

It is important to note that given the Arctic's unique atmospheric, marine and geophysical features, the data collected by Chinese Arctic scientific expeditions can be used to support future military deployments by Chinese armed forces to the region (Kossa 2024). This cross-over would not be surprising given the military-civil fusion strategy executed in China as well as the experiences of the US and the Soviet Union during the Cold War which implemented Arctic strategic science on a large scale to attain national security goals.

Given the resource potential of the Arctic region, some in the PRC view the Arctic as a future resource supply base for China that could prop up the PRC's economic security (Kossa 2024). Chinese state-owned enterprises (SOEs) have already invested in LNG projects in the Russian Arctic and shown interest in the mineral potential of Greenland. Similarly, Arctic shipping routes are viewed positively as possible shortcuts between China and the markets in Western Europe, leading to the development of the Polar Silk Road.

Chinese SOEs have been conducting shipping on sea routes in the Arctic Ocean since 2013 and data collected by Chinese Arctic scientific expeditions is used to support the commercial development of Arctic shipping routes. At the same time, through Arctic scientific and economic engagement, the PRC gains valuable knowledge in developing Arctic technologies (Sørensen and Hsiung 2021). The Arctic is a site for testing cutting-edge technologies under extreme conditions, such as autonomous underwater vehicles. This has significant implications for China's technological security as the country embarks on the quest to attain technological self-reliance.

Finally, the PRC's Arctic engagement also serves political security purposes. To uphold its legitimacy, the CCP seeks to meet domestic expectations concerning China's international status and prestige. By advancing Arctic infrastructure and enhancing observational capabilities, China signals to both domestic and international audiences that, under CCP leadership, it is a world-class technological power that is capable of challenging global deployments (Lajeunesse and Choi 2021).

The PRC and Arctic Governance

According to the PRC's Arctic White Paper, published in 2018, the Arctic region is seen as a global space in which extra-regional states have certain rights and privileges under international law such as navigation and scientific research. The White Paper also noted that the PRC will uphold the current Arctic governance system with the Arctic Council as its most important regional forum (SCIO 2018). Chinese officials have previously stated that China will not overstep its role as a non-Arctic state in the region, yet, at the same time they have indicated that China will not be absent from regional affairs. This is because the PRC sees itself as a near-Arctic state and an active Arctic affairs participant, builder and contributor.

However, there are indications that the PRC sees room for improvements in regional governance particularly when it comes to the roles of AC observers. Beyond the official government position on regional affairs, Chinese analysts and academics are much more vocal in their criticisms of Arctic governance. In particular, they see a privatization of regional affairs by Arctic states who, as they claim, seek to either exclude non-Arctic states from the region or restrict their access to it (Kossa 2024). A Chinese solution to this situation would be the implementation of a global and more inclusive governance system that would take into consideration the interests of stakeholders beyond the eight Arctic states.

In its bilateral relations with Arctic states, Russia emerged as China's premier Arctic partner. The two countries discuss Arctic cooperation in bilateral meetings, particularly in areas of resource extraction, scientific research and the development of the Northern Sea Route. They also conducted a joint patrol in Arctic waters in 2024. The PRC's relations with the US are affected by the unfolding great power competition between the two nations. China sees the American return to the Arctic as a reflection of Washington's Cold War mentality to suppress China. The Nordic states are still perceived in China as partners in areas of low politics, including scientific research, maritime safety, search and rescue, emergency responses, data sharing and technological cooperation. However, on the Nordic side, China is increasingly viewed as an intelligence threat which is negatively impacting Chinese Arctic scientific and commercial activities.

Going forward, given these dynamics, we will witness the emergence of a fractured Arctic – one that is based on Western/American principles and technologies and the other supported by enhanced Sino-Russian cooperation (Bertelsen 2022).

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